

Heterosis for biochemical constituents and protein profiles of elite rice hybrids of Tamil Nadu

Vijayalakshmi Dhashnamurthi^{1*}, Beena R² and Vijayalakshmi Chenniappan¹

¹Department of Crop Physiology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

² Regional Agricultural Research Station, Kerala Agricultural University, PATTAMBI, Kerala, India

* Corresponding author, Email: vijiphysiology@gmail.com

Abstract

Heterosis for grain yield is the outcome of several physiological as well as biochemical characters which have been relatively less investigated though their contribution is certain. Study was taken to assess the hybrid vigour of two high yielding rice hybrids namely CoRH 2(6.5t/ha) and ADTRH 1(7.0 t/ha) and their parents (IR 58025 A X C 20R; IR 58025 A X IR 66R respectively) in terms of some important physiological parameters such as chlorophyll content, soluble protein, variation in protein banding and nitrate reductase activity. All the physiological parameters were high in the hybrids than their parents throughout the crop growth period. Among the hybrids ADTRH 1, recorded higher chlorophyll content, soluble protein and Nitrate Reductase activity. The study on protein profiling showed differences in protein banding new protein bands between the parents and hybrids, while new bands of 90 kDa, 60kDa, 50kDa and 45kDa were present in the hybrids. Finally, the study revealed that ADTRH 1 performed better than CoRH 2.

Keywords

Rice, hybrids, heterosis, chlorophyll contents, soluble protein, SDS PAGE, Nitrate reductase activity

Abbreviations

NRase - Nitrate Reductase; SDS PAGE - Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate Poly-Acrylamide Gel Electrophoresis; kDa : Kilo Dalton; RUBPcase: Ribulosebiphosphate carboxylase; TDMP- Total Dry Matter Production.

Introduction

In India hybrid rice has progressed from an experiment to becoming a major source of rice production. The evolution of hybrid rice technology has generated high hopes in rice growing regions of Tamil Nadu for meeting the food demands of the ever growing population. It is generally felt that a yield plateau has been reached in conventional rice varieties and any further increase in the productivity of rice from current level could be achieved only through hybrid technology. India is yet to fully exploit the technology which offers a 10-15 per cent yield advantage over the best conventional inbred varieties [1]. Heterosis for grain yield is the outcome of several physiological as well as biochemical characters which have been relatively less investigated though their contribution is certain. Three major physiological traits that are always correlated with grain yield in hybrid rice are pigment composition, protein contents and enzyme activities like nitrate reductase activity. Chlorophyll contents gain importance because the net photosynthetic rate (P_n) of a rice cultivar was always correlated with the chlorophyll content of leaves [2]. Another important factor which influences the grain yield in rice is the protein content, as the leaf's soluble protein was the important material basis for rice's response to different concentrations of nitrogen [3]. Soluble protein content had important reference value for evaluating rice's nitrogen utilization efficiency which in turn is positively related to grain yield [4]. The

differential protein expression between the hybrid and its parents will be important for us to understand the possible molecular mechanisms for heterosis. To gain a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms for heterosis, proteomics serves as a powerful research tool. Again nitrate and ammonium are two major nitrogen sources for higher plants. The absorbed nitrate can then either be reduced by nitrate reductase (NR), a cytosolic enzyme, in the root, or transported to the shoot for assimilation, which contributes for grain yield. Importance of studying physiological traits has not been explored fully. However, traits like TDMP [5] in hybrid rice and water uptake were attempted [6,7]. Hence, the present experiment was designed to study the rice heterosis for chlorophyll content, soluble protein, with special attention to variations in the protein profiles, and nitrate reductase of important hybrids (CoRH 2 and ADTRH 1) of Tamil Nadu.

Materials and Methods

Location and Entries

The experiment was carried out at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore. The seeds of the parents (IR 58025 A X C 20R; IR 58025 A X IR 66R) and hybrids (CoRH 2 and ADTRH 1) were sown in June and harvested by September. The trial plot size was of 12m². The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with five replications and conducted during the kharif season under irrigated condition. Duplicate samples from five replications of both hybrids and parents were analysed for all

biochemical parameters at critical growth stages i.e. vegetative, flowering and maturity. The data were analysed statistically by finding out the Variety and Stage interaction effect using Systat for Windows version 6 as per the method of Wilkinson et al. [8]. Significance between different cultivars was compared at 0.05 probability levels using student t test.

Chlorophyll content

Measurements on Chlorophyll 'a', 'b' and total were made by following the protocol of Yoshida et al. [9]. About 0.1g of leaf samples was used for estimation of chlorophyll contents.

Soluble protein content:

The soluble protein content of the leaves was determined by measuring the color developed by the reduction of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent by the amino acids like tyrosine and tryptophan of protein, following the method of Lowry et al. [10] and expressed in mg g^{-1} FW.

Nitrate reductase

Nitrate reductase was determined as per the method of Hageman, [11]. The analysis was carried out using the physiologically matured leaf (Third leaf from top) and the activity was expressed as μ moles of $\text{NO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$ FW. The standard heterotic value was calculated over the mid parent using the formula, Heterotic value = F1- Mid parental value.

Protein profiling

Protein Extraction

For SDS-PAGE, leaf sheath tissues of both the parents and hybrids were ground to powder under liquid nitrogen and melted in ice-cold extraction buffer [50 mMTris-HCl, pH 8, 10 mMNaCl, 1% SDS, 5%

2- mercaptoethanol, 0.1 mM PMSF, 0.1 mM DTT], followed by centrifugation at 10,000 x g at 4°C for 15 min. Protein content of the clear supernatants obtained after centrifugation were determined using a Protein Assay Kit (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) with BSA as the standard. Extracts were stored at -20°C. The amount of protein was determined according to the method of Bradford [12].

One-Dimensional SDS-PAGE

Proteins, 5¼g of each sample, were separated by SDS-PAGE according to the method of Laemmli19. The separation was performed with a 10% separating gel and a 4% stacking gel using PROTEAN II Multi Cell (Bio-Rad). Electrophoresis was started at 10 mA constant current until the tracking dye entered the separating gel and continued at 25 mA until the tracking dye reached the end of the gel. After electrophoresis, the gel was stained with silver nitrate, according to the method of Damerval et al. [13]. Relative molecular weight (MW) of each protein was determined by using a standard curve generated from the standard proteins.

Results and Discussion

The chlorophyll content was high in the hybrids (ADTRH1 and CoRH2) than their parents throughout the crop growth period (Table 1). Between the hybrids, ADTRH1 showed very high chlorophyll content from vegetative to grain filling stage. The soluble protein content and nitrate reductase activity were also higher in hybrids. The protein profiling of both the parents and hybrids revealed that the hybrids exhibited new bands compared to parents. The hybrid ADTRH 1 showed better performance than CoRH 2 (Fig 1).

Parents/ Hybrids	Vegetative stage			Flowering Stage			Maturity Stage		
	Total Chlorophyll	Soluble protein	NRase activity	Total Chlorophyll	Soluble protein	NRase activity	Total Chlorophyll	Soluble protein	NRase activity
C20R	1.16±0.122	7.37±0.14	37.61±1.03	1.13±0.118	7.92±0.35	40.51±1.21	0.89±0.147	7.01±0.15	39.71±1.23
IR 58025 A	1.19±0.104	7.02±0.53	40.06±0.96	1.15±0.156	7.41±0.52	41.30±1.03	1.06±0.162	7.13±0.22	40.74±1.52
CoRH2	1.21±0.165	7.37±0.45	41.95±1.11	1.20±0.185	8.97±0.44	47.58±1.41	1.23±0.131	7.96±0.65	43.92±1.69
Heterotic value (%)	3.150	2.410	8.00	5.120	17.060	16.300	25.490	12.570	9.170
SEd	0.005	0.062	0.036	0.010	0.072	0.037	0.005	0.108	0.061
CD (0.005)	0.011	0.131	0.075	0.016	0.141	0.076	0.012	0.227	0.097

Table 1 Chlorophyll content (mg g^{-1}) soluble protein (mg g^{-1}) and NRase activity (μ moles $\text{NO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) of CoRH2 and its parents

Figure 1 Standard Heterosis for biochemical parameters in hybrid rice CoRH2 and ADTRH 1

Among the hybrids, ADTRH 1 showed more chlorophyll content than CoRH2 at all the

phenophases. In ADTRH 1 the chlorophyll contents were 2.37 mg/g; 2.30 mg/g and 2.27 mg/g during the vegetative, flowering and maturity stages respectively. While, in CoRH2 the chlorophyll contents were lesser compared to ADTRH 1 recording values of 1.21 mg/g; 1.20 mg/g and 1.23 mg/g at vegetative, flowering and maturity stages respectively. (Table 2). The chlorophyll content of the hybrids was found to be heterotic in various stages. This may be explained by the fact that, chlorophyll was an indicator of source size establishing a positive association with yield. Variation in chlorophyll content in rice was studied by Janoria et al. [14]. The Chlorophyll heterosis had been demonstrated in several studies by several authors [15,16,17]. The higher the chlorophyll content of leaves, they are likely to have high photosynthetic potential and thus higher yield potential [14,18,19].

Parents/ Hybrids	Vegetative stage			Flowering Stage			Maturity Stage		
	Total Chlorophyll	Soluble protein	NRase activity	Total Chlorophyll	Soluble protein	NRase activity	Total Chlorophyll	Soluble protein	NRase activity
C20R	1.95± 0.111	4.90± 0.23	32.0± 1.07	2.13± 0.122	4.67± 0.25	45.30± 1.22	1.21± 0.211	7.10± 0.62	44.0± 1.51
IR 58025 A	0.95± 0.121	5.60± 0.35	42.7± 1.33	0.45± 0.134	6.53± 0.33	57.00± 1.35	1.38± 0.185	7.30± 0.58	53.3± 1.38
CoRH2	2.37± 0.132	7.30± 0.52	46.7± 1.08	2.30± 0.143	7.77± 0.59	65.00± 1.14	2.27± 0.173	7.90± 0.39	65.3± 1.46
Heterotic value (%)	63.56	39.05	25.03	78.29	38.75	25.58	75.96	9.72	34.22
SEd	0.004	0.063	0.035	0.005	0.074	0.037	0.009	0.110	0.059
CD (0.005)	0.019	0.129	0.075	0.013	0.140	0.074	0.017	0.221	0.096

Table 2 Chlorophyll content (mg g⁻¹) soluble protein (mg g⁻¹) and NRase activity (μ moles NO₂ g⁻¹ h⁻¹) of ADTRH1 and its parents

About 50 percentage of the soluble protein in leaf extract is accounted for RUBPcase [20]. Hence, soluble protein content of leaves can be taken as a measure of RUBPcase activity. The hybrids recorded a higher content of soluble protein than the parents at all phenophases. The hybrid, CoRH2 recorded 4.7%; 11.73 to 17.42%; 10.42 to 11.9% increase in protein contents at vegetative, flowering and maturity phases over the parents. Similar trend was also observed in the hybrid ADTRH 1 which recorded an increased protein content of 23.28 to 32.87%; 15.95 to 39.89%; 7.59 to 10.13% at vegetative, flowering and maturity phases respectively over the parents. The positive heterosis showed by two hybrids at all stages suggests that high yielders have high levels of photosynthetic enzymes [20,21]. Measurement of soluble protein content might help in screening F1 hybrids for higher photosynthetic activity. Higher levels of favorable enzymes with higher activity per unit of soluble protein than the quantity itself for the various biochemical events

influenced the yield of heterotic hybrids [22]. Similar findings are also reported in hybrid cotton [17].

The heterosis for nitrate reductase activity was shown by ADTRH1 and CoRH2 at three different stages. Hageman et al. [23] provided evidence for enzyme heterosis. The enzyme activity was found to increase from seedling to flowering stage with a gradual decline at maturity in both the hybrids and the parents. ADTRH 1 recorded higher enzymes activities at all phenophases namely vegetative, flowering and maturity respectively (46.70 μ moles of NO₂ g⁻¹ hr⁻¹; 65.0 μ moles of NO₂ g⁻¹ hr⁻¹; 65.30 μ moles of NO₂ g⁻¹ h r⁻¹) compared to CoRH2 (41.95 μ moles of NO₂ g⁻¹ hr⁻¹; 47.58 μ moles of NO₂ g⁻¹ hr⁻¹; 43.92 μ moles of NO₂ g⁻¹ hr⁻¹). Similar results were reported in rice [24,25]. Nitrate reductase activity exhibited some heterosis in hybrids involving lower or medium nitrate reductase activity in parents [26]. The authors showed that nitrate reductase produces an optimum level of reduced leaf nitrogen that is responsible for enhanced efficiency of the

photosynthetic system in hybrids and in turn their productivity and yield. Sun et al. [27] has opined that there is a relationship between nitrate reductase activity and yield characters of hybrid rice during growth and development.

In an attempt to understand the molecular basis of heterosis, proteomics of SDS PAGE was used to identify the difference in protein banding of both the hybrids (CoRH2 and ADTRH1) and their parents (IR 58025 A X C 20R; IR 58025 A X IR 66R respectively). Detection of proteins was done by comparing patterns of parents and hybrids. Proteins were extracted from 21-day-old rice seedlings. Comparing the protein profiles in the leaf sheaths of parents and hybrids using SDS-PAGE revealed significant changes in the protein bands indicating changes at genotypic level. Some new protein bands appeared in both the hybrid plants when compared to the parents. New protein bands of the 90 kDa, 60 kDa and 50 kDa protein bands were found in leaf sheaths of ADTRH1 which were not present in their parental lines (IR 58025 A and IR 66R). Similarly, the hybrid, CoRH2 exhibited newer protein bands at 60kDa and 40kDa which were absent in its parental line (IR 58025 A and C 20R). (Fig 2). Furthermore, there was an enhanced expression of all other protein bands in the hybrids compared to parents. These results revealed that these proteins were expressed in specific genotypes. Similar results have been reported in rice [28] where the authors conclude that the proteins involved in photosynthesis, glycolysis, and disease/defense as well as their dynamic regulation at different developmental stages may be responsible for heterosis in rice. Similarly, it has been demonstrated that wheat hybridization can cause protein expression differences between the hybrid and its parents and these differentially expressed proteins were involved in diverse physiological processes that might be responsible for heterosis [29].

Lane 1: ADTRH1; Lane 2: CoRH2; Lane 3 IR 66R; Lane 4: C 20R; Lane 5: IR 58025 A

Fig 2 SDS-PAGE Profiles of polypeptides extracted from the leaf sheath of the hybrids and their parents (CoRH2 and ADTRH 1)

Conclusion

Heterosis is a common phenomenon in which the hybrids exhibit superior agronomic performance than either inbred parental lines. Although hybrid

rice is one of the most successful apothoses in crops utilizing heterosis, the physiological and molecular mechanisms underlying rice heterosis remain elusive. The results in this study suggest that the dynamic regulation of the important physiological processes at different developmental stages, such as chlorophyll contents, soluble proteins and nitrate reductase activity, may be one of mechanisms underlying heterosis in rice. The synthesis of new proteins expressed in the form of new protein bands in the hybrids may contribute to hybrid vigor in rice. The results in this study also clearly suggest that the performance of hybrid vigor was dependent on different development stages in rice.

References

1. Yang X and Sun X (1992). Physiological mechanism of varietal difference in rice plant response to low N level. *Acta Pedol Sin*, 29:73-79.
2. Liu ZQ, Liu ZY, Ma DP, Zeng SF (1984). A study on the relation between chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate of rice. *Acta Agron Sin*, 10 (1):57-62.
3. Li Xia, Sun Zhiwei, Jin Lei, Han Lei, Ren Chenggang, Wang Man and Lu Chuangen. (9 May, 2011). High/low nitrogen adapted hybrid of rice cultivars and their physiological responses. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 10(19): 3731-3738.
4. Zeng JM, Cui KH, Huang JL, Feng HE, Peng SB (2007). Responses of physio-biochemical properties to n-fertilizer application and its relationship with nitrogen use efficiency in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Acta Agronomica Sinica*, 33(7): 1168-1176.
5. Ramesh S, B Chandrasekaran, K Sathyamoorthi, C N Chandrasekhar and C Raja Babu (2007). Enhancing productivity of hybrid rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) CoRH2 through nitrogen management practices under transplanted and direct-seeding methods. *Journal of Food, Agriculture & Environment*, 5:314-323.
6. Vijayalakshmi D, Vijayalakshmi C, Djanaguiraman M and U Bangarusamy (2003). Physiological basis of heterotic vigor in rice seeds. *Madras Agric J*, 90: 545-547.
7. Ali abdallabasyouni Aboukhalifa (2009). Physiological evaluation of some hybrid rice varieties under different sowing dates. *Australian Journal of Crop Science Southern Cross Journals*, 3(3):178-183.
8. Wilkinson L, Hill M, Welna JP, Birkenbevel BK (1996). Systat for windows, Version 6 (ed) SPSS Inc, Evanston, IL, USA. . .
9. Yoshida S, Forno DA, Cock, JH and Gomez KA (1976). In: Laboratory manual for physiological studies in rice. *RRI*, 36-37.
10. Lowry OH Rosebrugh NJ, Farr, LA and Randall RJ (1951). Protein measurements with folin-phenol reagent. *J Biol Chem*, 193: 265-275.
11. Hageman, RH and Hucklesby DP (1971). Nitrate reductase from higher plants. *Methods in Enzymology*. Academic Press, New York, USA., 491-503.
12. Bradford MM (1976). A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding. *Anal Biochem*, 72: 248-254.
13. Damerval C, Guillox ML and de Vienne Blaisonneau D (1987). A simplification of Heukeshoven and Dernick's silver staining of proteins. *Electrophoresis*, 158-159.
14. Janoria, M.P. Vergara, B.S., Aguilar, A.M. and Park, F.S. (1990). Variation in chlorophyll content of rice flag leaf lamina and sheath. *International Rice Research News*, 15:2, 8-10.
15. Sinha, S.K., and R.Khanna. (1975). Physiological, biochemical and genetic basis of heterosis. *Adv Agron*, 27: 123-127.
16. Thangaraj M (1981). Physiology of heterosis in interspecific hybrid cotton - Varalaxmi (*Gossypium hirsutum* x *G. barbadense* L.). *Ph.D. Thesis, TNAU, Coimbatore.*, . .
17. Djanaguiraman M, Vijayalakshmi, C and D Vijayalakshmi (2002). Physiological basis of heterosis in cotton. *J Agricultural Resource Management*, 1(2): 102-106.
18. Mehta H, Sarkar KR, Sharma SK (1992). Genetic analysis of photosynthesis and productivity in corn. *Theor Appl Genet*, 84: 242-255.
19. Sarkar RK, Das S, Ravi I (2001). Changes in certain antioxidative enzymes and growth parameters as result of complete submergence and subsequent re-aeration of rice cultivars differing in submergence tolerance. *J Agron Crop Sci*, 187:69-74.

20. Smith H (1976). Ellis Fraction I Protein *Commentaries in Plant Science*, Pergamon Press, London (Ed.), 31-343.
21. Usuda H, Ku MSB. and Edward GE (1984). Rate of photosynthesis related to activity of photosynthetic enzyme: Chlorophyll and protein content among ten C3 species. *Aust J Plant Physiol*, 11: 509–517.
22. Hirel B, Bertin P, Quilleré I, Bourdoncle W, Attagnant C, *et al.* (2001). Towards a better understanding of the genetic and physiological basis for nitrogen use efficiency in maize. *Plant Physiol*, 125: 1258-1270.
23. Hageman RH, Leng ER and Dudley JH (1976.). A biochemical approach to corn breeding *Adv.Agron.*, 19: 45-86.
24. Govindaraj K and EA Siddiq (1986.). Hybrid vigour in rice with reference to morphophysiological components of yield and root density. *SABRAO J*, 18: 1-7.
25. Manonmani S, Ranganathan TB, Sree Rangasamy, SR Narasimman P and Suresh M (1993). Nitrate reductase (NRase) activity as an index for early maturity. *IRRN*, 18:3-26.
26. Li HZ, Jiang CM, Quan XJ, Jiang DZ, Lin ZW and Tag YW (1989). Nitrate reductase activities in the hybrids of *Oryza sativa* subsp. Japonica and their parents. *Hereditas*, 11: 9-10.
27. Sun J, Okita TW, Edwards GE (1999). Modification of carbon partitioning, photosynthetic capacity and O₂ sensitivity in Arabidopsis plants with low ADP- glucose pyrophosphorylase activity. *Plant Physiology*, 119,267 – 276.
28. Zhang Chunyan, Yan Yina, Aihong Zhang, Qingtao Lu, Xiaogang Wen, Zhen Zhu, *et al.* (2012). Comparative proteomic study reveals dynamic proteome changes between superhybrid rice LYP9 and its parents at different developmental stages. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 169: 387– 398.
29. Song X, Ni Z, Yao Y, Zhang Y, Sun Q (2009). Identification of differentially expressed proteins between hybrid and parents in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) seedling leaves. *Theor Appl Genet*, 118: 213-225.